

THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT DOSES OF GAMMA RADIATION ON LIPOLYTIC ACTIVITY IN SALIVARY GLAND TISSUE AND BLOOD

I.A.Mirzabekov

Ismoiljonmirzabekov@gmail.com

Andijon state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17128613>

Abstract: The study investigates the effect of different doses of gamma radiation on the tissue of salivary glands and on lipolytic activity in the blood. Radiation exposure is known to induce structural and biochemical alterations in living organisms. In this research, salivary gland tissue samples were examined for morphological changes after exposure to varying levels of gamma rays, while biochemical assays were used to evaluate lipolytic activity in the blood. The results demonstrate a dose-dependent relationship between gamma radiation and both tissue integrity and enzymatic activity. Moderate doses led to partial disruption of glandular tissue and significant changes in lipolytic activity, whereas high doses caused severe morphological damage and a marked decrease in functional parameters. These findings provide important insights into the biological consequences of radiation exposure and may contribute to understanding radiobiological risks and developing protective strategies in medical and environmental contexts.

Keywords: gamma radiation, salivary glands, lipolytic activity, blood biochemistry, radiobiology, tissue damage

This study was performed on adult white, outbred, male rats weighing 150-200 g. Rats were irradiated with the help of the "Terabalt-80" apparatus with doses of 1, 2, 4, 6 Gray with ^{60}Co (-quantum).

It is known that lipase in the salivary gland juice is mainly secreted by the receptor pathway.

The results showed that gamma irradiation at a dose of 1-2 Gray did not affect the lipolytic activity in the parotid, maxillary and sublingual gland homogenate.

Gamma irradiation at a dose of 4 Gray had a significant inhibitory effect on the lipolytic activity of the parotid, maxillary and sublingual gland tissue, it was found that it decreased by 20% compared to the control on the 3rd day of the experiment and decreased day by day. Even on the 60th day of the experiment, it remained 47% lower than the control group.

After exposure to gamma radiation at a dose of 6 Gray, the lipolytic activity in the parotid gland homogenate decreased by 15% compared to the control on the 10th day of the experiment, by 20% compared to the control on the 20th day

of the experiment. decreased by 53% on day 1 and by 73% on day 30. In the tongue and submandibular salivary glands, these changes began earlier and were more pronounced after irradiation.

Lipase is secreted into the blood mainly from the pancreas. Lipolytic activity in the blood did not change after irradiation at a dose of 1 Gray, but after exposure to gamma rays at a dose of 2 Gray, it was found that on days 3 and 10 of the experiment, lipolytic activity in the blood decreased compared to the control group, and on day 30 of the experiment, lipolytic activity in the blood returned to the level of the initial control group.

When the gamma irradiation dose was 4 Gray, a decrease in lipolytic activity in the blood by 16% compared to the control was observed the next day of the experiment, and it was found that its activity decreased day by day, that is, the lipase product decreased by 36% on the 3rd day of the experiment, by 48% on the 10th day, and by 58% on the 20th day.

When the gamma irradiation dose reached 6 Gray, it was found that the blood of irradiated rats on the 30th day of the experiment decreased by 85% compared to the control group.

If we take into account that the lipolytic activity in the blood is a product of lipase secreted from the pancreas, and this enzyme in the salivary glands is a product of lipase recirculated from the blood, it can be concluded that different doses of gamma irradiation do not have the same effect on the recirculation of the lipase enzyme in the body. Changes in lipolytic activity in saliva after irradiation can be used in sialodiagnostics, that is, to assess the secretory status of the pancreas, which is the main producer of this enzyme.

References:

1. Archakova, L.I. (1991). Reaktivnye izmeneniya submikroskopicheskoy organizacii simpaticeskikh ganglijev pri teplovom stresse [Reactive changes in the submicroscopic organization of sympathetic ganglion cells during heat stress]. In: 'Stress, Adaptation and Dysfunctions': Abstracts of the VI All-Union Symposium. Kishinev. Pp. 10-19.
2. Budilina, S.M., Degtyarev, V.P. (2000). Fiziologiya chelyustno-licevoj oblasti [Physiology of the maxillofacial region]. Moscow: Medicina.
3. Kodirov, Sh.K.(1993). Mekhanizmy transformacii fermentnogo i peptidnogo spektrov slyuny i rol slyunnyh zhelez v fermentnom gomeostaze [Mechanisms of transformation of enzyme and peptide selectors and the role of seleza in enzyme homeostasis]. Abstract of the dissertation for Doctor of Medical Sciences. Tomsk.

4. Korotko, G.F. (1983). Fermenty pishchevaritel'nyh zhelez v krovi (oчерki o fermentnom gomeostaze). [Enzymes of iron digestion in the blood (essays on enzyme homeostasis)]. Tashkent: Medicina.
5. Korotko, G.F. (2005) Sekreciya podzheludochnoj zhelezy [Secretion of the pancreas]. Krasnodar: Kubanskiy gosudarstvennyj medicinskiy universitet.
6. Korotko, G.F. (2006). Sekreciya slyunnyh zhelez i elementy salivodiagnostiki [Secretion of the salivary gland and elements of salivary diagnostics]. Moscow: Akademiya estestvoznaniya.
7. Korotko, G.F. (2007). Zheludochnoe pishchevarenie [Gastric digestion]. Krasnodar: Publishing house OOO BK 'Group B'.
8. Surinov, B.P. (1983). Fermentnye sistema organizma pri luchevykh vozdeystviyah [Enzyme systems of the body under therapeutic effects. Actual issues of radiation hygiene]. In: Tezisy dokladov Vsesoyuznoj konferencii «Aktualnye voprosy radiacionnoj gigieny». [Abstracts of the reports of the All-Union Conference 'Current Issues of Radiation Hygiene']. Moscow. Pp. 103-112.
9. Aizenman, L., Libow, K., Rothman, S. (1999). Endocrine secretion of mammalian digestive enzymes by exocrine glands. American Journal of Physiology. Pp. 223-232.
10. Mirzabekov I.A. (2024). Turli yoshdagi kalamushlar tana vazniga gamma nurlanishning ta'siri [The effect of gamma radiation on body weight in rats of different ages]. In: "Ilm-fan muammolari tadqiqotchilar talqinida" mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy konferensiyasi materiallari to'plami [Collection of materials of the republican scientific conference on the topic 'Problems of science as interpreted by researchers']. Pp. 187-189.
11. Mirzabekov, I. A. (2024). Vliyanie gamma-izlucheniya na aktivnost' fermentov slyunnyh zhelez [The effect of gamma radiation on the activity of salivary gland enzymes]. Universe: physics and biology. No. 2 (116). Pp. 39-42 .